

Density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity studies of cardo group containing symmetric double Schiff bases solutions at 303, 308 and 313 K

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Abstract : The density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity (2 MHz) of pure solvents e.g. chloroform, DMF, 1,4-dioxane and symmetric double Schiff bases solutions have been investigated to understand the effect of solvents on molecular interactions at 303, 308 and 313 K. Various acoustical parameters such as U (ultrasonic velocity), Z (specific acoustical impedance), κ_s (isentropic compressibility), R (Rao's molar sound function), b (Van der Waals constant), π (internal pressure), V_f (free volume), L_f (intermolecular free path length), $(\alpha/f^2)_{Cl}$ (classical absorption coefficient) and τ (viscous relaxation time) have been determined and correlated with concentration (C). Good to excellent correlation between a given parameter and concentration is observed at all temperatures (T) and solvent systems studied. Linear or non-linear increase or decrease of acoustical parameters with concentration and temperature indicated the existence of strong molecular interactions. The linear or non-linear increase of S_n with C and decrease with T further supported the existence of molecular interactions.

Keywords : Ultrasonic velocity, acoustical parameters, density, viscosity, solute-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions, Schiff bases.

Introduction

Schiff bases are useful as fine chemicals, medical substrates and ligands for metal complexes and find their industrial application as antifungal and biological applications¹⁻⁴. They are also useful for the synthesis of drugs like antibiotics, antiallergic, antiphlogistic and antitumor⁵⁻¹² and for dyes, liquid crystals and powerful corrosion inhibitor¹³⁻¹⁵.

To our knowledge no work has been reported on ultrasonic studies of symmetric double Schiff bases of 1,1'-bis(4-amino phenyl)cyclohexane. The objective of the present work was to investigate the effect of concentration, temperature, solvents as well as nature of Schiff bases on ultrasonic and related acoustical properties of Schiff bases (1).

SDSB-1 : R = H

SDSB-2 : R = 4-CH₃

Theoretical equations for acoustical parameters :

Specific acoustical impedance :

$$Z = U\rho \quad (1)$$

Isentropic compressibility :

$$\kappa_s = \frac{1}{U^2\rho} \quad (2)$$

Rao's molar sound function :

$$R = \frac{M}{\rho} U^{1/3} \quad (3)$$

where M is the apparent molecular weight of the solution and can be calculated according to eq. (4) :

$$M = M_1W_1 + M_2W_2 \quad (4)$$

where W_1 and W_2 are weight fractions of solvent and solute, respectively; M_1 and M_2 are molecular weights of solvent and solute, respectively.

Van der Waals constant :

$$b = \frac{M}{\rho} \left[1 - \left[\frac{RT}{MU^2} \right] \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{MU^2}{3RT}} - 1 \right] \right] \quad (5)$$

where R is the gas constant and T is the temperature.

Internal pressure :

$$\pi = b'RT \left(\frac{K\eta}{U} \right)^{1/2} \frac{\rho^{2/3}}{M^{7/6}} \quad (6)$$

where R is the gas constant and b' (2) is the packing factor and K (4.28×10^9) is a constant. The π depends on temperature, density, sound velocity and specific heat at constant pressure.

Free volume :

$$V_f = \left[\frac{MU}{K\eta} \right]^{3/2} \quad (7)$$

where $K = (4.28 \times 10^9)$ is constant.

Intermolecular free path length :

$$L_f = K (\kappa_s)^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

where $K = (93.875 + 0.375T) \times 10^{-8}$ is a temperature dependent constant.

Classical absorption coefficient :

$$\left(\frac{\alpha}{f^2} \right)_{Cl} = \frac{8\pi^2\eta}{3U^3\rho} \quad (9)$$

Classical absorption coefficient has its origin in the vis-

cosity of the medium.

Viscous relaxation time :

The resistance offered by viscous force in the flow of sound wave appears as a classical absorption associated with viscous relaxation time :

$$\tau = \frac{4\eta}{3\rho U^2} \quad (10)$$

Solvation number :

$$S_n = \frac{M_2}{M_1 \left(1 - \frac{\kappa_s}{\kappa_{s_1}} \right) \left(\frac{100 - X}{X} \right)} \quad (11)$$

where X is the number of grams of solute in 100 g of the solution.

Results and discussion

The density, viscosity and velocity data of pure solvents and SDSB-1 and SDSB-2 solutions at 303, 308 and 313 K are reported in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. It is observed graphically that ρ decreased linearly with concentration (C) and temperature (T) in CF system, while it is increased linearly with C and decreased with T in DMF and DO systems. Viscosity increased linearly with C and decreased with T in all the systems studied. Ultrasonic velocity increased with C and decreased with T in CF and

Table 1. Density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) data of SDSB-1 solutions at different temperatures

Concn. (mol/L)	Density, ρ (kg/m ³)			Viscosity, $\eta \times 10^3$ (Pa.s)			U (ms ⁻¹)		
	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
SDSB-1 + CF									
0	1465.7	1460.9	1457.3	0.619	0.574	0.554	959.0	945.4	924.6
0.01	1458.7	1455.5	1452.9	0.643	0.618	0.589	961.2	953.6	943.4
0.02	1455.1	1451.9	1449.1	0.679	0.628	0.602	963.6	957.2	947.4
0.04	1451.6	1448.0	1445.4	0.705	0.640	0.625	967.4	960.6	953.0
0.06	1448.1	1444.0	1441.6	0.728	0.676	0.652	968.8	963.6	957.4
0.08	1444.8	1440.7	1438.4	0.752	0.701	0.675	970.6	967.4	960.6
0.10	1442.5	1437.8	1435.7	0.776	0.724	0.697	973.2	969.6	963.6
SDSB-1 + DMF									
0	932.8	927.5	916.4	0.848	0.815	0.777	1451.4	1458.6	1464.4
0.01	946.3	944.5	943.7	0.984	0.934	0.878	1453.6	1464.4	1466.6
0.02	948.7	946.8	946.4	1.020	0.979	0.946	1461.2	1469.8	1473.2
0.04	951.2	948.9	948.3	1.080	1.037	1.014	1469.4	1477.2	1479.8
0.06	953.6	951.4	950.6	1.130	1.080	1.055	1476.8	1483.0	1484.8
0.08	954.2	952.9	951.5	1.180	1.118	1.080	1482.8	1488.8	1491.8
0.10	955.9	954.9	953.8	1.220	1.158	1.120	1487.4	1492.8	1497.4

Table-1 (contd.)

SDSB-1+ DO									
0	1043	1039	1035	1.100	1.042	1.015	1327.4	1319.6	1291.8
0.01	1044	1040	1036	1.120	1.056	1.014	1341.6	1339.6	1325.2
0.02	1045	1043	1039	1.160	1.067	1.033	1349.0	1347.4	1331.2
0.04	1048	1046	1043	1.190	1.111	1.059	1356.8	1349.6	1339.2
0.06	1051	1049	1046	1.230	1.131	1.074	1362.4	1353.0	1345.4
0.08	1054	1052	1050	1.260	1.175	1.127	1369.0	1361.2	1353.0
0.10	1057	1056	1054	1.310	1.227	1.178	1369.6	1365.2	1357.4

Table 2. Density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) data of SDSB-2 solutions at different temperatures

Concn. (mol/L)	Density, ρ (kg/m ³)			Viscosity, $\eta \times 10^3$ (Pa.s)			U (ms ⁻¹)		
	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
SDSB-2 + CF									
0	1465.7	1460.9	1457.3	0.620	0.574	0.554	959.0	945.4	924.6
0.01	1460.0	1454.1	1451.7	0.643	0.600	0.577	961.6	946.4	927.6
0.02	1456.2	1450.6	1449.0	0.669	0.624	0.619	963.4	949.6	930.8
0.04	1452.6	1446.8	1446.2	0.720	0.661	0.668	967.4	953.2	936.4
0.06	1449.0	1443.1	1442.8	0.779	0.726	0.734	971.2	958.4	941.4
0.08	1443.6	1439.8	1439.7	0.817	0.770	0.738	976.8	963.4	945.4
0.10	1440.3	1438.0	1436.9	0.861	0.814	0.782	981.6	967.6	949.4
SDSB-2 + DMF									
0	932.8	927.5	916.4	0.848	0.815	0.777	1451.4	1458.6	1464.4
0.01	946.1	944.8	943.3	0.985	0.906	0.883	1457.2	1463.4	1469.2
0.02	948.8	947.2	946.6	1.032	0.953	0.946	1463.2	1471.2	1475.2
0.04	951.2	949.8	948.9	1.085	1.007	0.994	1470.8	1477.6	1481.4
0.06	953.6	952.8	952.0	1.145	1.068	1.042	1479.6	1484.4	1491.4
0.08	955.4	954.6	954.3	1.199	1.118	1.107	1487.0	1493.0	1497.2
0.10	957.2	956.5	956.2	1.239	1.171	1.138	1492.8	1499.4	1505.4
SDSB-2 + DO									
0	1043	1039	1035	1.103	1.042	1.015	1327.4	1319.6	1291.8
0.01	1044	1040	1037	1.104	1.048	1.026	1343.4	1337.0	1332.4
0.02	1046	1044	1042	1.132	1.077	1.057	1350.8	1344.6	1341.4
0.04	1048	1047	1045	1.182	1.123	1.107	1356.8	1353.0	1351.2
0.06	1051	1050	1048	1.229	1.167	1.143	1364.2	1360.4	1356.4
0.08	1055	1054	1052	1.258	1.204	1.179	1371.0	1365.2	1363.6
0.10	1058	1057	1054	1.296	1.233	1.219	1376.8	1373.0	1369.2

DO systems, while in DMF system it is increased with T for both the Schiff bases. The least square equations along with correlation coefficients are reported in Tables 3 and 4 from which it is clear that a good to excellent correlation is observed in each case. From Tables 1 and 2 it is clear that the change in ρ and U with C and T are not appreciable as η because molecular motion is much more affected by solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions in the solutions¹⁶⁻¹⁸. The increase in ρ , η and U with C

confirmed increase in cohesive forces because of strong molecular interactions, while decrease in these parameters with T support decrease in cohesive forces. The increase in temperature has two opposite effects namely structure formation and structure destruction. The structure forming tendency is mainly due to solute-solvent interaction, while destruction of structure formed previously is due to thermal fluctuations^{17,18}. When thermal energy is greater than that of interaction energy, it causes

Table 3. The correlation equations and correlation coefficients for SDSB-1 solutions

Parameter	Correlation equations (Correlation coefficients, γ)		
	303 K	308 K	313 K
	SDSB-1 + CF		
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	-175.62C + 1459.2 (-0.991)	-192.19C + 1456.2 (-0.993)	-185.51C + 1453.4 (-0.991)
η (mPa.s)	1.374C + 0.643 (0.986)	1.228C + 0.603 (0.987)	1.212C + 0.577 (0.999)
U (ms ⁻¹)	125.15C + 961 (0.983)	172.93C + 953.07 (10.992)	220.55C + 942.84 (0.987)
$\kappa_s \times 10^{+10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	-2.541C + 7.738 (-0.983)	-1.689C + 7.559 (-0.989)	-1.015C + 7.420 (-0.962)
$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	-0.419C + 5.7067 (-0.964)	-0.729C + 5.761 (-0.985)	-0.994C + 5.826 (-0.989)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	-0.95C + 4.182 (-0.998)	-0.797C + 4.090 (-0.998)	-0.75C + 4.083 (-0.985)
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m ³)	-2.735C + 2.589 (-0.997)	-3.443C + 2.92 (-0.964)	-3.639C + 3.053 (-0.996)
	SDSB-1 + DMF		
ρ (kg m ³)	101.18C + 946.2 (0.972)	110.79C + 944.18 (0.991)	103.15C + 943.72 (0.982)
η (mPa.s)	2.653C + 0.967 (0.997)	2.405C + 0.927 (0.991)	2.481C + 0.887 (0.966)
U (ms ⁻¹)	366.47C + 1452.9 (0.987)	312.11C + 1463.2 (0.991)	327.34C + 1465.4 (0.994)
$\kappa_s \times 10^{+10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	-2.931C + 5.003 (-0.983)	-2.591C + 4.945 (-0.991)	-2.647C + 4.934 (-0.992)
$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	-1.397C + 4.682 (-0.987)	-1.189C + 4.655 (-0.992)	-1.257C + 4.65 (-0.983)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	-6.700C + 5.638 (-0.999)	-5.381C + 5.266 (-0.971)	-6.010C + 5.276 (-0.983)
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m ³)	6.786C ² - 0.7843C + 1.304 (0.992)	12.68C ² - 1.116C + 1.405 (0.947)	27.143C ² - 2.687C + 1.503 (0.876)
	SDSB-1 + DO		
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	146.58C + 1042.3 (0.999)	175.07C + 1038.5 (0.991)	199.73C + 1034.2 (0.994)
η (mPa.s)	2.047C + 1.106 (0.996)	1.854C + 1.031 (0.989)	1.756C + 0.991 (0.980)
U (ms ⁻¹)	267C + 1345.3 (0.973)	236C + 1341.1 (0.978)	331C + 1325.4 (0.996)
$\kappa_s \times 10^{+10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	-3.088C + 5.323 (-0.981)	-2.893C + 5.368 (-0.984)	-3.831C + 5.517 (-0.993)
$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	-1.444C + 4.8 (-0.985)	1.337C + 4.85 (-0.980)	-1.723C + 4.917 (-0.994)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	-4.877C + 5.225 (-0.996)	-4.635C + 5.033 (-0.992)	-4.782C + 4.949 (-0.982)
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m ³)	-10.536C ² + 1.529C + 1.2 (0.940)	-15.714C ² + 1.796C + 1.3626 (0.992)	-16.439C ² + 2.22C + 1.406 (0.963)

Table 4. The correlation equations and correlation coefficients for SDSB-2 solutions

Parameter	Correlation equations (Correlation coefficients, γ)		
	303 K	308 K	313 K
	SDSB-2 + CF		
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	-214C + 1461.3 (-0.996)	-177.37C + 1454.6 (-0.988)	-161.07C + 1452.7 (-0.998)
η (mPa.s)	2.446C + 0.622 (0.998)	2.409C + 0.575 (0.998)	2.201C + 0.573 (0.976)
U (ms ⁻¹)	222.36C + 958.84 (0.997)	234.36C + 944.32 (0.999)	241.48C + 926.02 (0.996)
$\kappa_s \times 10^{+10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	-2.265C + 7.4412 (-0.994)	-2.770C + 7.7073 (-0.998)	-3.174C + 8.026 (-0.994)
$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	-0.931C + 5.715 (-0.995)	-1C + 5.81 (-1)	-1.120C + 5.930 (-0.997)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	-23.892C ² + 4.094C + 4.051 (0.983)	-6.785C ² + 2.628C + 4.01 (0.972)	-54.633C ² + 7.390C + 4.007 (0.915)
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m ³)	-7.587C + 2.760 (-0.983)	-8.815C + 3.026 (-0.992)	-8.102C + 2.985 (-0.923)
	SDSB-2 + DMF		
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	105C + 946.94 (0.997)	117C + 945.16 (0.994)	123C + 944.22 (0.997)
η (mPa.s)	2.797C + 0.97 (0.996)	2.876C + 0.889 (0.997)	2.746C + 0.876 (0.989)
U (ms ⁻¹)	395.01C + 1454.0 (-0.99)	384.82C + 1461.6 (0.99)	393.81C + 1466.3 (0.997)
$\kappa_s \times 10^{+10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	-3.322C + 5.004 (-0.989)	-3.129C + 4.945 (-0.985)	-3.203C + 4.929 (-0.998)
$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	-1.548C + 4.682 (-0.996)	-1.403C + 4.656 (-0.993)	-1.496C + 4.647 (-0.993)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	-7.625C + 5.449 (-0.999)	-6.765C + 5.29 (-0.999)	-6.951C + 5.323 (-0.991)
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m ³)	14.357C ² - 1.386C + 1.326 (0.876)	14.359C ² - 1.976C + 1.523 (0.892)	28.729C ² - 3.685C + 1.609 (0.930)
	SDSB-2 + DO		
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	153.97C + 1042.4 (0.996)	179.73C + 1039.4 (0.993)	178.63C + 1037.1 (0.982)
η (mPa.s)	2.120C + 1.090 (0.995)	2.065C + 1.03 (0.995)	2.084C + 1.010 (0.996)
U (ms ⁻¹)	358.19C + 1342 (0.994)	379.18C + 1335.9 (0.990)	387.67C + 1332.3 (0.983)
$\kappa_s \times 10^{+10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	-3.466C + 5.325 (-0.995)	-3.7885C + 5.387 (-0.990)	-3.899C + 5.387 (-0.981)
$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	-1.542C + 4.828 (-0.993)	-1.792C + 4.863 (-0.988)	-1.819C + 4.881 (-0.981)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	-5.752C + 5.174 (-0.999)	-5.473C + 5.043 (-0.999)	-5.340C + 4.991 (-0.998)
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m ³)	0.585C + 1.268 (0.892)	0.59C + 1.360 (0.898)	0.51C + 1.397 (0.956)

destruction in structure formed previously. The density and viscosity of the medium, pressure, temperature, etc. affect the ultrasonic velocity. Strong molecular interactions result increase in viscosity, i.e. solvophilic behavior of the solute under study.

In order to understand molecular interactions in solutions the effect of concentration, temperature, nature of solvents and Schiff bases are examined through various acoustical parameters as determined according to above mentioned standard relations. Acoustical parameters are correlated with C at three temperatures and for a given Schiff base-solvent system. The least square equations and correlation coefficients for selected parameters are reported in Tables 3 and 4. The concentration and temperature dependence of acoustical parameters furnish valuable information about strength of molecular interactions occurring in the solutions. A good to excellent correlation between a given parameter and C at three temperatures is observed. Whenever nonlinear behaviors are observed, polynomial correlations are performed.

It is observed that Z ($\gamma = 0.956-0.998$) increased linearly with C and decreased with T except DMF system in which it is increased linearly with T . Isentropic compressibility is decreased linearly with C and increased with T . Similarly, R ($\gamma = 0.999-1.000$) and b ($\gamma = 0.999-1.000$) both increased linearly in all the systems but practically no temperature effect is observed. Free path length decreased linearly with C and increased linearly with T except DMF system in which it is decreased with T . Internal pressure decreased linearly with C and T for SDSB-1 in all three solvent systems. In case of SDSB-2, π increased nonlinearly with C and decreased with T in CF system, while in DMF and DO systems, it decreased linearly with C and T . For SDSB-1 + CF, V_f decreased linearly with C and increased with T , while it increased nonlinearly with C and T in DMF and DO systems. For SDSB-2 + CF, V_f increased linearly with C and decreased with T , while in DMF and DO systems it increased linearly with C and T . Viscous relaxation time ($\gamma = 0.949-0.999$) and classical absorption coefficient ($\gamma = 0.921-0.989$) both increased linearly with C and decreased with T . The increase or decrease of above mentioned parameters with C and T justified the presence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions. Isentropic compressibility, internal pressure, free volume and free path length are influenced by concentration, temperature, nature of solvents and solutes. Decrease in π and increase in V_f and L_f indicated decrease in cohesive forces and vice versa.

Viscous relaxation time and classical absorption coefficient are influenced by ρ , η and T .

Solvation number is a powerful tool in deciding strength of the molecular interactions in the solutions. The plots of S_n against C at three temperatures are presented in Figs. 1 and 2 from which it is clear that SDSB-1 and SDSB-2 have structure forming tendency in the studied solvent systems. For SDSB-1, S_n increased linearly with C and decreased with T in all the three solvent systems. In case of SDSB-2, S_n increased nonlinearly with C and decreased with T . The decrease in S_n above 0.060 mol L⁻¹ indicated presence of powerful solute-solute interaction over solute-solvent interaction. The observed trend

Fig. 1. The plots of S_n against C for SDSB-1 at 303, 308 and 313 K in CF, DMF and DO.

Fig. 2. The plots of S_n against C for SDSB-2 at 303, 308 and 313 K in CF, DMF and DO.

is : CF > DMF > DO. Thus, CF has the maximum solvation tendency while DO has the least tendency. The decrease in S_n with increasing T further supported destruction of structure formed previously as a result of thermal fluctuations. Azomethine and methyl are the groups which interact with electropositive parts of the solvents and hence undergo solvation and while interactions with electronegative parts of the solvent undergo destruction of the structure formed previously. Thus, dipole-dipole interactions of opposite type favor solvation, while of the same type favor disruption of the structure formed previously.

Experimental

Materials :

The solvents chloroform (CF), *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) and 1,4-dioxane (DO) used in the present study were of laboratory grade and purified according to literature methods¹⁹. Schiff bases were synthesized according to our recent work²⁰. The stock Schiff bases solutions (0.10 M) were prepared in above mentioned solvents and from them a series of solutions were prepared (0.01–0.1 M) at room temperature.

Measurements :

The density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) of pure solvents and Schiff bases solutions were carried out at 303, 308 and 313 K by using specific gravity bottle, Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer and Mittal Enterprise Interferometer (New Delhi) Model No F-81, operating at 2 MHz, respectively. The ρ , η and U measurements were accurate to $\pm 0.1 \text{ kg/m}^3$, 0.01 mPa.s and $\pm 0.15\%$, respectively.

Conclusions :

Following facts are observed from experimental findings :

- Various acoustical parameters have suggested the existence of powerful molecular interactions in the solutions.
- SDSB-1 and SDSB-2 have structure forming tendency in the studied solvent systems.
- In case of substituted Schiff bases, solute-solute interactions are powerful over solute-solvent interaction above 0.060 mol L⁻¹ concentration.
- The observed solvation trend is : CF > DMF > DO.

References

- A. P. Mishra, M. Khare and S. K. Gautam, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2002, **32**, 1485.
- C. Bi and Y. Fan, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2004, **34**, 687.
- M. G. Bhowan, T. Jeewoth and H. L. Kam-wah, *Transition Metal Chem.*, 1999, **24**, 445.
- S. H. Abdel-Hafez, *Phosphorus, Sulfur and Silicon*, 2003, **178**, 2563.
- M. V. Solvskii, N. V. Nikolaskaya and N. A. Zaikina, *Pharmaceutical Chemistry Journal*, 2002, **36**, 9.
- V. E. Kuzmin, V. P. Lozitsky, G. L. Kamalov, R. N. Lozitskaya, A. I. Zheltvay, A. S. Fedtchouk and D. N. Kryzhanovsky, *Acta Biochimica, Polonica*, 2000, **47**, 867.

7. V. P. Lozitsky, V. E. Kuzmin, A. G. Artemenko, R. N. Lozytska, A. S. Fedtchouk, E. N. Muratov and A. K. Mescheriakov, *SAR and QSAR in Environmental Research*, 2005, **16**, 219.
8. V. S. Agarwala, A. R. Krishnaswamy and P. K. Sen, "Synthetic lubricating oil and greases containing chelates of Schiff base", U.S. pat., 1992, 5147567.
9. M. D. Tarafder, A. Kasbollah, N. Saravanan, K. A. Crouse, A. M. Ali and K. T. Oo, *J. Biochem., Mol. Bio. and Biophys.*, 2002, **6**, 85.
10. K. D. Patel, B. D. Mistry and K. R. Desai, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 783.
11. Yu. V. Popov, T. K. Korchagina and G. V. Chicherina, *Russian J. Org. Chem.*, 2001, **37**, 677.
12. H. Temel, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2004, **57**, 723.
13. I. Kraicheva, P. Finocchiaro and S. Pailla, *Phosphorus, Sulfur and Silicon*, 2004, **179**, 2345.
14. S. Bilgic and N. Caliskan, *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, 2001, **31**, 79.
15. H. Ma, S. Chen, L. Niu, S. Zhao, S. Li and D. Li, *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, 2002, **32**, 65.
16. S. Das, R. P. Singh and S. Maiti, *Polym. Bull.*, 1980, **2**, 403.
17. W. Bell and R. A. Pethrick, *Polymer*, 1982, **23**, 369.
18. R. A. Pethrick and B. T. Poh, *Brit. Polym. J.*, 1983, **15**, 149.
19. J. A. Riddick, W. B. Bunger and T. Sakano, Vol. II, 4th ed., Wiley-Interscience Publication, John Wiley, New York, 1986.
20. B. J. Gangani and P. H. Parsania, *Spectrosc. Lett.*, 2007, **40**, 97.